

An Overview of Library Networks in India

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Abstract

This paper deals with the concept of a library network. The objectives of library networks have been discussed in this article. Planning Commission efforts also discusses in this paper. Several components have been discussed in this paper. Different types of networks like Local Area Network (LAN), Metropolitan Area Network (MAN), and Wide Area Network (WAN) have been mentioned in this article. The configuration of computer systems or network devices connected to one another is known as a network topology. Various network topologies have been emphasized in this paper. Libraries are frequently referred to as resource sharing centers. Few library networks have been highlighted in this article.

Keywords Library Networks, Local Area Networks, Metropolitan Area Networks, Wide Area Networks, Network Topology.

Introduction

A network is a formal organization that facilitates cooperation and resource sharing. It is divided into subgroups with the exception that the majority of a library's needs will be met by the subgroups to which it belongs. Conversely, a group of gadgets (often called nodes) linked together by communication channels. Any device that can send and/or receive data created by other nodes on the network is referred to as a node. A network, in its widest definition, is made up of two or more items or entities that share resources and data. Libraries nowadays are unable to meet the information needs of their patrons due to the explosion of information and the rapidly rising costs of information services and goods. In the past, to satisfy user expectations, resource sharing techniques like Inter-Library Loan (ILL) were employed. Libraries now operate in a networked environment where data and information resources are shared electronically and are accessible in electronic format. The ability for several users to share data and other information resources is the primary benefit of the library network. Information can be transferred swiftly, accurately, and consistently through the library network. (Library networks: national and international)

A lengthy history of collaboration in librarianship gave rise to the idea of the library network. The foundation of a library network is identified when one library offers services to another library. In general, a library network is defined as an association of libraries that have reached a consensus to support one another in meeting the information needs of their patrons. A network is defined as two or more libraries involved in a shared pattern of information exchange through communications for some functional purpose by the National Commission on Libraries & Information Science in its National Programme Document (1975). (Jebaraj and Devadoss, 2004)

Aim of study

The aims of the study are-

1. To study in detail about the library networks as a means of resource sharing among the libraries.
2. To identify the objectives of library networks.
3. To identify the different role of library networks in India.

4. To introduce new services in the library.

Review of Literature

There are an extensive number of studies on library networks conducted in India as well as abroad. Among these, recent selected studies are included in this review.

Some of the most significant library networks in India are briefly highlighted in the current study by **Jadhav (2022)**. There is also discussion of the objectives, services, functions, future prospects and stages of completeness of these library resource sharing networks. The current study, conducted by **Suresha and Priscilla (2019)**, provides a brief overview of some of the world's largest library consortia and networks. The objectives, functions, services, future prospects and stages of completeness of these library resource-sharing networks are also discussed. The article draws its conclusion by briefly mentioning the obstacles to the development of these networks and library consortium. **Mohapatra and Vandana (2018)** discussed the historical background of resource sharing and the role of Library Networks and Resource Sharing in Academic Library Systems. It also discussed about the policy, terms and conditions for resource sharing among the participate libraries. List of library networks and library consortia have been also mentioned in this paper. This paper reviews the present literature of resource sharing in the context to the Management institute libraries in Bangalore city of India by **I N and Rao AN (2017)**. **Joshi (2014)** discussed the objectives, functions, characteristics of digital library and Indian library networks for e-learning, etc. in the view of demand of user in the utilization of information in digital format. **Valarmathy and Kaliyaperumal (2014)** focused on the comparative study of the nine library networks on the basis of the sponsorship, objectives, services, functions etc. In this article, **Valarmathy and Kaliyaperumal (2013)** made an effort to outline the current state of the nation's library networking systems. In addition, a study of the challenges in developing a single public library network system and a public library network system proposal for Tamil Nadu are included in the paper. A thorough description of Indian academic library networks has been provided, and this study also presents the current state of Indian special library networks. The article also looks at network issues, and it concludes with a number of recommendations for enhancing networking in India. In addition, this study presents a few potential library networks that are based on research. **Jebaraj and Devadoss (2004)** discusses network development in India. Types of networks have been mentioned in this paper. Different library networks have been discussed in this article.

Main Text

Objectives of Library Networks:

Several objectives of library networks are mentioned below-

- i) To encourage cooperative efforts and resource sharing among libraries by offering dependable and effective methods of resource sharing.
- ii) By offering automation tools, to raise service standards and optimize resource usage at each library.
- iii) To coordinate initiatives for the establishment of an appropriate collection and, whenever feasible, eliminate needless duplication.
- iv) To set up reference centers to oversee and assist with catalogue searches and to keep an online union catalogue of all the member libraries' books, serials, and non-book materials centrally located.
- v) To create a specialized bibliographic database that will allow users to search and access books, serials, and non-book resources.
- vi) Arranging for the sharing of information for library use among other regional, national, and worldwide networks. (Library networks)

Planning Commission Efforts:

The Indian government's Planning Commission has been very interested in library networks and resource sharing. Its efforts throughout the 1985–1990, Seventh Five Year Plan have increased in several areas. In November 1983, the Commission established a working group to modernize informatics and library services. The working committee turned in their report in July of 1984. Among other things, it suggested connecting library systems via library networks. The Seventh Plan was to take this report into consideration. Another Working Group was created by the Commission, and it turned in its findings in May 1989. It again recommended among others interlinking of library systems in the

country. A Core Task Group was established by the Planning Commission in February 1995 to draft a paper outlining a strategy for increasing the contributions of science and technology to the sharing of library resources. A working group on libraries and informatics was once more established by the Commission and placed under the Department of Culture, Ministry of Human Resources Development, Government of India. The group's report was to be taken into consideration for the Ninth Plan, which ran from 1997 to 2002. Many significant proposals for the nation's libraries' modernization and networking are included in the report of the Commission Working Group. The implementation of NISSAT, UGC, Planning Commission, and other government agencies in India has resulted in heightened endeavors towards the creation of library networks and automation. (Library networks: Indian scenario)

Components:

Different components of library networks are discussed below:

i. Human Network: The most crucial element of a library network is its workforce, and that workforce's readiness to engage with the network and pool resources from their individual libraries. Although the availability and delivery of information are the main concerns of a library network. Human resources are what enable this.

ii. Online Databases: A library network's foundation is made up of databases and databanks. Information sharing is the root notion behind the concept of online databases. A database is a collection of all the entire data about a subject that is non-redundant, multiuse, independent, and physically accessible. The data is organized and structured to enable interactive searches by users. A library network may create some databases on its own and purchase or license databases from other database creators.

iii. Computer Hardware and Software Infrastructure: In order to host databases and databanks that it creates and maintains, a library or information network needs computer hardware and software infrastructure. The purpose of the servers is to enable member institutions' access to databases, digital assets, browse, and search interfaces. Communication equipment such as switches, routers, hubs, repeaters, modems, and other devices needed to set up a Local Area Network (LAN) would also be needed for a library network. A multitude of software packages are also needed for a library network in order to manage its highly specialized and diverse resources, activities, and services. Many software packages are needed to manage the many parts and functions of a library network.

iv. Data Networks: In order to a library network's servers to be reachable by its members, they must be connected to the Internet. The infrastructure of other data networks and Internet service providers is used by the majority of library networks.

v. Members: The membership of a library network serves of its effectiveness. A larger membership base lends greater significance and efficacy to a library network. The expenses incurred in keeping a library network operational and running, such as licensing and hosting databases belonging to third parties, are divided among subscribers and network members. (Library and information networks and consortia)

Types of Network:

Network may be divided according to their scope of area. They are as follows:

i. Local Area Networks (LAN)

ii. Metropolitan Area Networks (MAN)

iii. Wide Area Networks (WAN)

i. Local Area Networks (LAN): A LAN is a computer network that consists of access points, cables, routers, and switches that enable devices to connect to web servers and internal servers within a single building, campus, or home network, and to other LANs via WAN or MAN. A single internet connection can be used to access and exchange data between devices on a Local Area Network (LAN), which are mostly workstations and personal PCs. (Local area network)

ii. Metropolitan Area Networks (MAN): A MAN is a type of computer network that links users to computer resources within an area roughly equivalent to a metropolitan area.

When Local Area Network (LANs) in a city are connected to form a single, bigger network that can potentially provide an efficient connection to a wide area network, this is referred to as a Metropolitan Area Network, or MAN. The phrase is also used to refer to the process of connecting multiple Local Area Network (LAN) in a city by means of point-to-point connections. (Metropolitan area network)

iii. Wide Area Networks (WAN): The technology that links offices, data centers, cloud storage and applications is called a WAN. Because it extends beyond a single structure or sizable campus to encompass numerous locations dispersed throughout a particular region, or possibly the entire globe, it is known as a Wide Area Network. For instance, WANs are used to link office networks in companies with numerous foreign branch offices. The internet is the greatest Wide Area Network (WAN) in the world since it is made up of numerous interconnected worldwide networks. (What is WAN?)

Network Topology:

A network topology is the arrangement with which computer systems or network devices are connected to each other. Topologies may define both physical and logical aspect of the network. Both logical and physical topologies could be same or different in a same network. The various network topologies are:

i. Point-to-Point: It is a type of topology that works on the functionality of the sender and receiver. It is the most basic form of communication between two nodes, where the sender and the recipient are the two nodes. High bandwidth is provided by point-to-point. (Types of network topology)

ii. Bus Topology: In a bus topology, a single communication line or cable is shared by all devices. Bus topology may encounter issues when several hosts are sending data simultaneously. In order to resolve the problem, bus topology either employs CSMA/CD technology or designates a single host as the bus master. It's a basic kind of networking where the failure of one device doesn't impact the others.

iii. Star Topology: All hosts in Star topology are connected to a central device, known as hub device, using a point-to-point connection. That is, there exists a point to point connection between hosts and hub. The hub device can be any of the following:

- a. Layer-1 device such as hub or repeater.
- b. Layer-2 device such as switch or bridge.
- c. Layer-3 device such as router or gateway.

iv. Ring Topology: This form of network architecture creates a circular network structure by connecting each host system to precisely two other machines. Data passes via all intermediate hosts when a host tries to connect or send a message to a host that is not nearby. An additional cable may be all that the administrator needs to connect one more host to the current configuration.

v. Mesh Topology: A host connects to one or more hosts in this topology type. In this topology, all hosts are connected point-to-point to each other, or some hosts may only be connected point-to-point to a small number of other hosts.

vi. Tree Topology: Another name for tree topology is hierarchical topology. At the moment, this is the most often used type of network topology. This topology borrows characteristics from bus topology and mimics an extended star topology. The network is divided into several tiers or layers by this topology. A network is divided into three categories of network devices, mostly in LANs. The access layer, to which computers are connected, is the lowest. Serving as a mediator between the top and lower layers, the middle layer is also referred to as the distribution layer. The topmost layer, referred to as the core layer, serves as the network's center hub, or the root of the tree from which all nodes branch out. (Computer network topologies)

Library Networks:

Few library networks are discussed below-

i. Developing Library Network (DELNET): Founded in 1988 and incorporated as a society in 1991, DELNET was formerly known as Delhi Library Network till 2001. It was first supported by NISSAT, DSIR, and is currently being jointly promoted by the Department of Information Technology, Ministry of Communications and Information Technology, Government of India, and the National Informatics Centre (NIC). Apart from accomplishing the goals of the library network, DELNET also conducts research in the fields of information science and technology, develops new systems, implements research findings, and disseminates them.(Library networks: national and international)

Activities and Services: a) Union Catalogue of Books, Periodicals.

b) Database of Periodical Articles.

c) Database of Theses and Dissertations.

d) Database of E-books.

e) Online Inter Library Loan.

f) Document Delivery Services. (DELNET)

ii. INFLIBNET: Information and Library Network is referred to by the term INFLIBNET and located at Gandhinagar, Gujarat. It is a major national programme of the University Grants Commission (UGC) initiated in the year 1991. INFLIBNET is an Autonomous Inter University Center run by UGC. In 1996, it became a stand-alone inter-university center. Additionally, INFLIBNET is making a significant effort to provide efficient file transfers, computer/audio/video conferencing, bulletin board postings, email, and other forms of communication amongst researchers and academicians in India.(Library networks: national and international)

Activities and Services: a) Library Automation (INDCAT, SOUL 3.0 etc.)

b) E-Consortium (E-SODHSINDHU, N-LIST, SHODHSHUDDHI etc.)

c) Open Access Initiative (SHODHGANGA, SHODHGANGOTRI, SHODH-CHAKRA, INSTITUTIONAL REPOSITORY etc.)

d) Scholarly Network (VIDWAN: EXPERT DATABASE, IRINS etc.)

e) E-content Development and Services (E-PG PATHSHALA, UGC MOOCS etc.)

f) Rankings and Accreditation (NIRF, NAAC etc.) (INFLIBNET Centre)

iii. CALIBNET (Calcutta Library Network): Established in 1986 in accordance with the Societies Registration Act, 1961 of the West Bengal Government. CALIBNET is a project funded by NISSAT, DSIR and managed by the Calcutta Society. During its initial phase, CALIBNET connected 38 scientific and technological computerized libraries in the Calcutta metropolitan area. It then connected to additional regional metropolitan area networks.

Activities and Services: a) Database services.

b) Full-text Document Delivery Services.

c) On-line CD ROM based global Information search and retrieval services.

iv. MYLIBNET (Mysore Library Network): It was situated on the Central Food Technological Research Institute (CFTRI) Campus in Mysore. MYLIBNET was established by NISSAT, DSIR in 1995. For LIS workers, MYLIBNET arranges a variety of training courses.

Activities and Services: a) Union Catalogue of Periodicals.

b) To enable quicker communication between all libraries using the Electronic Mail service.

v. MALIBNET (Madras Library Network): The MALIBNET started in the year 1991 and aims to offer efficient information services to those residing in and around Madras. In 1993, MALIBNET registered as a society. For the MALIBNET project, the executing agency was INSDOC, which is now known as NISCAIR. MALIBNET welcomes universities, colleges, R&D centers and individuals as members.

Activities and Services: a) E-mail Service.

b) Photocopy Service.

c) Document Delivery Service.

d) Training Courses.

vi. BONET (Bombay Library Network): BONET started in the year 1994. BONET is backed by NISSAT and DSIR. More than 25 libraries have signed up to become members. It offers professional development training programs and seminars in addition to providing access to databases, CD-ROMs, and other media.

Activities and Services: a) Online Catalogue of Periodicals, Books etc.

b) Online Document Delivery of Items.

vii. PUNENET (Pune Library Network): PUNENET is an initiative including the National Chemical Laboratory (NCL), the University of Pune, and the Centre for Development of Advanced Computing (C-DAC). This project, funded by NISSAT was started in the year 1992. PUNENET is housed in Bio Informatics Centre, Pune.

Activities and Services: a) Union Catalogue of Periodicals.

b) Databases of Booksellers and LIS Professionals.

c) Current Awareness Service (CAS).

d) Online Search Facility.(Library networks: national and international)

viii. ADINET: ADINET is a Advance Information Network of Libraries in Gujarat. It was established in 1994 with an initial grant for a few years from National Information System for Science and Technology (NISSAT), Department of Science and Industrial Research, Government of India, New Delhi. It caters to all types of Libraries: school, college, universities, institutional libraries and even public libraries. Hence, access is provided to hundreds of libraries, librarians and organizations through the ADINET Network.

Activities and Services: a) Inter Library Loan.

b) Database of Current Periodicals.

c) Document Delivery Services.

d) Published Newsletter.

e) Librarians' Day Celebration. (Advance Information Network of Libraries in Gujarat)

Conclusion

The library networking has improved the processing and management of information. It is necessitated by information explosion which is used to describe the impetuous speed at which information is being generated and disseminated in different formats. It is also a result of rising demand for high-quality information and insufficient funding, which makes it nearly impossible for a single information organization to obtain all information resources in all of their formats. In the last few years, a sizable number of libraries have formed networks. As a result, user realize that library and information systems has changed significantly since computer networking became a widely recognized component of the infrastructure. The traditional library has undergone tremendous transformation as a result of the new digital media environment. Because digital information is instantly available, as user information demands are likewise shifting from traditional documents to digital

information. Thus, library networking is progressive in order to satisfy user's needs as quickly as possible.

References

1. Advance Information Network of Libraries in Gujarat. Retrieved from <https://www.alibnet.org/cms/Introduction.html>
2. Computer network topologies. (n.d.). *tutorialspoint*. Retrieved from https://www.tutorialspoint.com/data_communication_computer_network/computer_network_topologies.htm
3. DELNET. Retrieved from <https://delnet.in/index.html>
4. INFLIBNET Centre. Retrieved from <https://www.inflibnet.ac.in/activities/>
5. I N, P. and RAO AN, J. (2017). Resource Sharing and Networking of Management Libraries: A Pre-Research Approach. *International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research*, 15(15), 265-273. Retrieved from https://serialsjournals.com/abstract/11738_ch_27_f_-_prakash.pdf
6. Jadhav, D.J. (2022). Library Networking in India: A Study. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology (IJARSCT)*, 2(4), 426-434. Retrieved from <https://ijarsct.co.in/Paper13494.pdf>
7. Jebaraj, F.D. and Devadoss, F.R. (2004). Library and information networks in India. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 6(2), 1-8. Retrieved from <https://core.ac.uk/reader/17214660>
8. Joshi, N.M. (2014). Digital library and library networks in India. *Global Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 3(1), 37-44. Retrieved from https://www.ripublication.com/gjal/gjalv3n1_04.pdf
9. Library and information networks and consortia. Retrieved from <https://egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/35260/5/Unit-9.pdf>
10. Library networks. Retrieved from <https://pawankumarjha.tripod.com/dissertation/chapter2.html>
11. Library networks: Indian scenario. Retrieved from <https://pawankumarjha.tripod.com/dissertation/chapter3.html>
12. Library networks: national and international. Retrieved from <https://egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/26309/1/Unit-2.pdf>
13. Local area network. Retrieved from <https://www.heavy.ai/technical-glossary/local-area-network>
14. Metropolitan area network. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Metropolitan_area_network
15. Mohapatra, N. and Vandana, D. (2018). Resource Sharing & Library Networks in India. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, IT and Social Sciences*, 8(12), 233-236. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351869653_Resource_Sharing_Library_Networks_in_India
16. Suresha, N. and Priscilla, N.S. (2019). Library networking and consortia. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR)*, 6(2), 141-151. Retrieved from <https://www.ijrar.org/papers/IJRAR19K2160.pdf>
17. Types of network topology. Retrieved from <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/types-of-network-topology/>
18. Valarmathy, N and Kaliyaperumal, K. (2013). Indian Library Networks: Myth or Reality. *Indian Journal of Library and Information Science*, 7(3), 335-349. Retrieved from https://rfppl.co.in/subscription/upload_pdf/ijlis3_1299.pdf

19. Valarmathy, N. and Kaliyaperumal, K. (2014). Comparative Study on Indian Library Networks. *IJSTE - International Journal of Science Technology & Engineering*, 1(2), 5-12. Retrieved from <https://www.ijste.org/articles/IJSTEV112012.pdf>

20. What is WAN?. Retrieved from <https://aws.amazon.com/what-is/wan/>